

Research Article

Delay Factors Evaluation of Nigerian Seaports (A Case Study of Apapa Ports Complex, Lagos)

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Abstract

The study set out to evaluate delay causative factors in Nigerian ports industry using the Apapa ports complex as a case study. Commencing with a pilot survey, the researcher was able to identify several delay factors working together to reduce efficiency in Nigerian ports industry. These variables formed the independent variables. With a well structured questionnaire, the respondents were asked to rank each of the delay factors according to their respective perception of the influence of each factor on delay factors at the port. The monthly ranking values of the delay factors from the respondents were cumulated into annual values for the study. The annual values or rankings were then subjected into multi-regression analysis. The beta coefficients of the variables were calculated hence the ones with positive coefficients were identified as critical factors. However, the beta coefficients of all the delay factors were used in modeling the forecasting equation for delay problem in the port, the major task of the study.

Key words: turnaround time, pilot survey, delay causative variables, critical factors, ranking, cumulative values.

Background of the Study

Human society and especially today as business life is structured by time – tight schedules. Time has been established as an expensive good. Ship voyage plan takes account of the time spent and its value. Voyage is a function of two variables viz: (i) transit time (ii) port time

With improvement in speed of most modern ships, transit time of ship has been reduced to the barest minimum. This has led to a focus of voyage plan relative to time in port in present days. This is considering in the usual marine destination/ port choice model. (Konig, 2002). Similarly, the average waiting time of vessels in Nigerian ports has been reduced very drastically as most berths remain empty, yet the average turnaround time of vessels remain higher compared to the experiences in other west and central African countries. (See tables 1 to 3).

Table 1: Turnaround Time of Ships in General Cargo Berth, Apapa Lagos 2002-2006.

Year	Average waiting time in days	Average service time in days	Average total turnaround time in days
2002	0.75	3.46	14.21
2003	0.87	14.53	15.40
2004	0.51	12.64	13.15
2005	0.62	15.45	16.07
2006	0.61	11.12	11.73
Total	0.36	67.20	70.56
Average	0.67	13.44	14.11

Source: NPA annual report 2007

Table 2: Turnaround Time Of Ships In General Cargo Port, Tokaradi Ghana 2002-2006.

Year	AWT	AST	ATRT
2002	0.35	6.25	6.60
2003	0.43	4.53	4.96
2004	0.42	4.42	4.84
2005	0.51	4.76	5.27
2006	0.44	4.23	4.67
Total	2.15	24.19	26.34
Average	0.43	4.84	5.27

Source: Fair shipping, Ghana authoritative maritime news magazine 2007

Table 3: Turnaround Time Of Ships In General Cargo Port Tema Ghana 2002 – 2006

Year	AWT	AST	ATRT
2002	0.65	3.20	3.87
2003	0.53	3.10	3.63
2004	0.43	2.88	3.31
2005	0.53	3.50	4.03
2006	0.57	3.80	4.37
Total	2.73	16.48	9.21
Average	0.55	3.29	3.84

Source: Tema port information 2007

The inefficiency in Nigerian ports became more obvious when compared to the turnaround time of ships in a developed country Australia.

See Table 4: Average Turnaround Time Of Ships In Albany Port, Australia General Cargo Port 1999-2003.

Year	AWT in hours	ATRT in days
1999	77	3.2
2002	75	3.1
2001	84	3.5
2002	73	3.04
2003	81	3.4
Total	390	16.24
Average	78	3.25

Source: Albany port, western Australia

Nigerian ports are not users friendly as seen on the table presented. In a world of competitiveness, inefficiency in port operation and management brews high cost of doing business in ports which spells doom to the economy. In such a situation, the port inefficiency which manifest in delays and high costs of using the ports in an advantageous positions. Here, the neighboring ports attract vessels and cargo traffic originally scheduled for Nigerian ports. The inability of the inefficient port to improve means total boycott of the port by the ,liners.

Table 5: Comparative West African Sub-Region Port Traffic/ Dues On Cargo

Charges in USD/ MT	Nigeria	Benin Republic	Senegal	Ghana	COV	Cameroon
Harbor dues	2.50	2.10				
Stevedoring	4.00	2.40	4.90	4.08	3.56	4.78
Extra service	3.00					
Total	9.50	4.50	4.90	4.08	3.56	4.78

Source: Report and analysis of NPA operations and tariffs by Nigerian shipping community 2002 (unpublished).

Table 6: Freight Rates On Containerized Cargo From Far-East Korea To Nigeria And Benin Republic Ports (Lagos And Contonou) In 2002.

Container size	Freight rate to Lagos port	Freight rate to contour
1x20	\$9,000	\$7,500
1x40	\$16,000	\$16,000

Source: Tomline shipping company Lagos

Statement of the problem

According to Konig (2002) shippers as well as ship owners calculate a utility for each alternative port and choose the port which shows the highest utility or time efficiency. In other words, when a ship operator chooses a port of destination, he does not only think of reaching the port in time but also the reliability of leaving the port in time. Consequently, he thinks of reliability of such service in alternative ports.

A higher utilization of the vessel will only be achieved if time in port is improved which will signify that fixed cost by the operator will be spread over increased number of voyage. This will consequently lead to reduced cost of ship operation. Chin-Yuan and Wen-Chin (2001) agreed that time and cost are highly correlated as far as port business is concerned. They opined that efficient terminal operation will shorten the total time of a ship in ports and increase the number of voyages made over a period.

Traditionally, the turnaround time of a ship in port is a function of two variables namely

- (i) Waiting time or queuing time
- (ii) Service time

The time of a vessel in port is high when either of the two is high compared to normal or the combination of the two. Waiting time is always high when the demand for berths is higher than the supply. Here the major task of a port planner is to serve the annual vessels efficiently often referred to as the design capacity.

In order to tackle the problem of delay in Nigerian ports most especially high turnaround time, the government had embarked on so many reforms which includes the expansion programme between 19809-1985. The new ports construction agenda gave birth to many ports including the Apapa general ports complex Lagos. With the many ports in Nigeria the problem of inefficiency shifted away from that shortage of berths relative to ship traffic to high service time cum high turnaround time.

The objectives of the study

The discussion so far in the study has shown that turnaround time of ships in ports is a major determinant of cost of doing business in the port. Using quantitative and qualitative approaches the study is aimed at fulfilling these specific objectives.

- (i) To identify and assess the key determinants of delays in Nigerian ports.
- (ii) To determine the relationship between delays and the various delay causative factors relative to Apapa ports complex, Lagos
- (iii) To investigate the role or influence of each causative factor in determining port delay level in Apapa port.
- (iv) To shed some light on the differences in environment or location relative to delays in ports. (disaggregate approach).
- (v) To determine which delay causative factors are critical or most influential to the Apapa port operator in an attempt to reduce or eliminate abnormal delay.

Research questions

In order to achieve the objectives of this research study, the study will attempt to provide answers to the following research questions.

- (i) What is the relative degree of importance or influence exerted by the various delay causative factors on delay as perceived by the respondents?
- (ii) What is the relationship between turnaround time of ships in Apapa ports and delay causative factors.
- (iii) To what extent do these delay factors collectively determine the level of delays in the study location Apapa port?
- (iv) To what extent do each of these delay factors determine the level of delay in Apapa port?

Hypothesis to be tested

To provide answers to the research questions, the following hypothesis will be tested.

- (i) There is in relationship existing between delay / turnaround time of ships in the port (Apapa port) and the delay causative factors.
- (ii) That there is no difference between the degrees of influence exerted by each delay factors on the turnaround times observed. In other words, there is no significant difference in the mean score of each of the delay causative variable.
 $H_0 = U_1 = U_2 = U_3 \dots U_n$
 $H_1 = \text{Alternative hypothesis } U_1 \neq U_2 \neq U_3$
- (iii) That the relationship between delays and each of the various delay variables is positive and high. The strength of association between delay and the explanatory variables will be measured to identify the critical factors, the major task of the study.

The significance of the study

The purpose of the study is to determine the weight of the various delay causative factors as experienced in Apapa port Lagos. This has become very necessary in that it help in identifying the critical factors among the variables. This makes the study very significant and different from previous studies under taken to investigate port performances. Previous studies like UNCTAD (1991) had focused on the determination of optimal berths of a port using the traditional queuing model as a tool of data analysis. Other studies such as Ugboma et al(2006) had focused on service qualities that attract shippers and ship owners to specific ports. Ha(2003), Lim et al(2004), Tongzon (2002), Clerk et al (2001), Koi Yu (2006) have all done studies on the assessment of port attractiveness in various ports of the world. The above works showed that researchers have done a lot of studies on port attractiveness and choice of ports by shippers and ship owners. However, none of these studies has tried to identify the critical factors among the delay causative factors which translate to high monetary costs prevalent to the Nigerian ports as seen in Apapa port complex. In other words, these previous studies failed to captured the relationship between the critical causative factors and the value of delays observed. For instance, Okon (2004) identified shallow channel as a port delay causative factor but failed to estimate the degree of influence this single factor has on the total delay value experienced in the port relative to other delay determinants. The truth remains that no study has actually focused on the identification of delay critical factors. There must be a relationship between these delay causative factors and the level of delays experienced at Apapa port. This the study tends to found out or investigate.

It is worthy to note that most of these studies mentioned earlier end their works when they arrive at the conclusions that one port is more attractive to other e.g. Apapa port is more attractive to ports user than Port Harcourt port or Tema port Ghana is more attractive than Lagos port complex Nigeria. They have not taken the pain to assess the influence of each of the delay determinant factors on the delay value. The knowledge of the critical factors will help management in the assessment of risk of delay expected in each voyage to the port. The study tries to establish the links between each causative factor and the delay value, which the previous studies neglected. The study is unique and significant in that it has concentrated on readily qualitative factor notably time of ship in port as against the previous studies that attach more interest in quantitative factors such as reputation, personal relation and port regulation.

Scope and limitation of the study

The study evaluates the performance of Apapa ports complex against some specific objectives. These are turnaround time of ships in the study location (Apapa port) in Nigeria and cost of doing business in the port. In other words, it looks at port performance in Nigeria at disaggregate level it tries to investigate the existing relationship between delay level observed and the relative delay factors identified.

To be precise, the study will use Apapa ports complex as a case study and make comparison with ports of Tema, Tokaradi Ghana, Albany port in Western Australia. The study is a preliminary and pioneering work in an attempt to seek for an alternative way of solving the problem of high turnaround time of ships in Nigeria ports.

Scarcity of funds as well as time constraints did not permit the survey to cover all the ports in Nigeria. The actual survey period is twelve months, January to December 2007.

The data collection combined both primary and secondary sources.

Brief review of literatures

According to Okotie and Attah (2005), a seaport is a subsystem of the maritime transportation system. It is an essential organ of the transportation system of a nation. A seaport is also recognized as an entry point for goods coming into a country from other countries just as it is an exit point for goods leaving the country for other countries. There is a positive relationship existing between a ship and a port. This relationship Esra and Walters (1979) described as a servant / master relationship. In other words, the main function of a port is to provide all necessary facilities to accumulate calling ships as well as enable the ships load and off load cargoes.

Clerk et al (2001) consequently described a port as an enterprise that must provide quality service to her customers to survive economically. This is because shippers as well as ship owners demand efficient services from port operators for continuous patronage. Ugboma et al sees a port as a service facility that need to be equipped properly to service her master efficiently if its usefulness and performance level is to be recognized. According to Ugboma, just as the shipping industry's usefulness, efficiency and overall performance is evaluated in the light of services rendered to the ships, so also the usefulness of the seaports relate to the entire economy. The number of customers to a commercial organization determines the viability of the enterprise. Likewise, the volumes of ship traffic to a port determine the prosperity and life of the port.

Huybrechts et al agrees with Ugboma that a seaport is a centre of attraction. As a service centre its viability is measured by the volume of ship and cargo traffics attracted to it over a period of time they conducted a survey evaluating the attractiveness of the port of Anteverp to shippers and ship owners. They were able to identify several factors that determine port choice in a competitive environment.

Using China as a case study Tiwan et al (2003) applied stated preference choice model in assessing port selection behavior by shippers and ship owners.

Tongzon (2002) conducted similar survey in South East Asia. Using a survey questionnaire approach, Tongzon targeted the relationship existing between shippers/ship owners and choice of ports or port's attractiveness. These studies all concluded that service quality was very important in port attractiveness to customers. Tongzon (2002) specifically identified a few choice determinants namely time efficiency shipping frequency to the port, infrastructural availability, port location, port charges, response to port user's need, reputation for cargo damage claims etc. these factors are what attract customers to the port. It must be emphasized that most of these determinant relates positively to delays in the ports. In his conclusion, Tongzon identified time efficiency as the factor that rated highest among other factors. This is consistent with the global trend and practice. With the adoption of modern logistical approach like "just in time" delivery, Tongzon is of the opinion that high value added products need to be delivered in time or pass through the port fastly to avoid high charges accumulation.

Time in port has always been a major or an important determinant of port attraction to port users. Koi Yu (2006) assessed the attractiveness of ports in the North European container transshipping market.

Koi concluded that Hamburg and Rotterdam are the most attractive port user's option. Consequently they act as transshipment hub within European markets. Antwerp and Bremenhaven container terminals followed closely behind whereas Felistowe and La. Havre are the least attractive options requiring substantial improvements in quality service delivery mostly time in port to change the current situation.

Alpharliner (2005) assessed port attractiveness through soliciting the opinions of shipping lines that are the major and direct port users. He used a targeted survey respondents consisting of chief executives officers, general managers, operation managers, district managers, purchasing managers, including various maritime transport scholars and shipping consultants. His conclusion deviated slightly from the other studies discussed earlier. Though loading and loading facilities, accommodation for large volume shipments, frequency, port charges, assistance in claim flexibility, ability in meeting special handling requirements were recognized as port choice determinants he rated the availability of information flow very high. Other studies that investigated port choice or attractiveness includes Song and Yeo (2004), Dey (2004), Begnon (2002), Chivolka and Raith (2001), Livet et al (2004). The employed an analytical hierarchy process (AHP) to examine predominant factors that have bearing on port selection decision by shippers. AHP is a multi-objective or multi-criteria theory of measurement.

The study methodology

First a pilot study was conducted in which a number of personal unstructured interviews with top executives of shipping companies, port operators, freight forwarders, cargo agents and dock workers were interviewed. This was done to discuss the purpose of the research study.

Apart from delay causative factors identified from the literature, the pilot study highlighted some of the delay determinant variables from the long experiences of using the ports as well as operating in the Apapa ports complex by the respondents. The results helped in constructing the questionnaire used. In other words the pilot survey

identified twenty (20) variables. However to reduce the determinant variables to a manageable size, factor analysis was applied to these relevance variables to collapse then to ten (10) independent factors namely

- (a) Inadequacies of Berths
- (b) Lack of Cargo Handling Equipment
- (c) Lack of manpower
- (d) Scarcity of skilled manpower
- (e) Administrative bottleneck
- (f) Deliberate attempt by port workers to extort money from port users
- (g) Lack of storage facilities
- (h) Insufficient depth of the entry channels
- (i) Too many public holidays and strikes
- (j) Too much idle time due to equipment break down and absence of night operations.

The respondents which numbered fifty (50) were asked to rank each of the delay factors according to how strong each feel that each factor may influence delay. The most important factor to the respondent earns a maximum of ten (10) marks. The next factor earns nine (9) marks etc.

The monthly rankings of each of the delay causative variables by the respondents were cumulated to arrive at the yearly rankings of the delay causative factors. This seemed very interesting for the purpose of analyzing the relationship between causative factors and the delay values. By so doing the most critical factors are those factors which posed heavy constraints in the achievement of efficient port operations especially in the area of high turnaround time of ships in Apapa port complex. Since the problem of delay causative factors cannot be tackled at a time, it implies that given a particular budget for port operation, much emphasis must be channeled to the critical factors. These are the most serious factors relative to the high turnaround time, therefore preference must be accorded them.

The Population/ Sample Size of the Study

The population of the study comprises of the entire service providers and all port users in Apapa ports complex. The service providers consists of staff of Nigerian ports authority (former port operators) the staff of the private terminal operators, the dockworkers as presently managed by Nigerian maritime administration and safety agency (NIMASA). The port users consist of the staff of all the shipping companies as well as clearing and forwarding companies.

It was not easy to have the staff population of these organizations, the assumption here is that the population is large. Consequently, there was adoption of a judgment or purposive technique to arrive or determine those to be interviewed (sample size). Purposive sample is drawn because of the ease of data collection or special features of the members of the sample. Therefore, the selection of the sample units is based on the assumption that the field officers or interviewers can identify those to serve the research purpose. The study therefore could not adopt a random approach because of the unknown population size. The terminal based approach which the study adopted got statistical information at the point of operation where the causative factors distort port operations. The study is therefore operations conscious.

The total of fifty (50) questionnaires were administered at the study location, Apapa ports complex as follows

Shipping Agents (shipping lines)	= 10
Shippers (freight forwarders)	= 10
Nigerian Ports Authority	= 10
Private terminal operators staff	= 10
Dockworkers (NIMASA) staff	= 10

Methods and Tools for Data Analysis

From the discussion so far, the following research questions relative to Apapa ports complex operation including the ones earlier raised are identified. These research questions form the basis for the selection of tools for data analysis.

- (i) Which delay causative factors are the most influential on Apapa ports complex delays?
- (ii) Which among them is most significant or critical?
- (iii) What is the effect of tackling the problem of the critical factors on ships time in port?
- (iv) Does the elimination of these critical factors improve the turnaround time of ships in port.

To answer these questions calls for the application of multi-regression model. The multi-regression techniques helped in performing correlation analysis of the relationship between the delay determinants and the delay values. In other words, the technique looked at the delay causative factors at disaggregate level.

Multi-regression technique believes that there are critical causative factors that determine delay in port. The list of these factors is inexhaustible. You can add more and more factors according to environment location in an attempt to build a port delay model, the major task of the study.

In the multi-regression analysis, the coefficients of each delay variable $X_1, X_2 \dots X_n$ determine the weight or influence of each causative factor. Consequently, a partial analysis on each causative factor is conducted to determine change in Y (time in port) the dependent variable relative to X_1 when $X_2 \dots X_n$ are held constant. To determine the values of a, b_1, b_2 etc which represent the coefficients of the independent variables (causative factors), calls for the solving of three multi-regression equations simultaneously.

$$\begin{aligned}\sum Y &= na + b_1 \sum X_1 + b_2 \sum X_2 \\ \sum X_1 Y &= a \sum X_1 + b_1 \sum X_1^2 + b_2 \sum X_1 X_2 \\ \sum X_2 Y &= a \sum X_2 + b_1 \sum X_1 X_2 + b_2 \sum X_2^2\end{aligned}$$

MODELING

One of the major output expected from the study is the overall delay model for Apapa ports complex respondents were asked to show their perception on each delay causative factor relative to the level of delay observed at the study location. This was modeled using a multivariate regression analysis that links delay to causative factors. This is a very useful tool in dealing with variable relative to many explanatory variables to establish the relationship between each explanatory variable and the turnaround time of ships in the port.

The basic model will look like this;

$$Y_{it} = A_0 + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + e_i$$

Where $X_{11}, X_{21}, X_{31}, \dots X_{in}$ delay variable

i = any port, e = error, t =time

Data Presentation and Analysis

The assessment of the degree of influence, each causative factor has on delay values involves the determination of the probability distribution of the cumulative rankings of the respondents on each delay causative variable. In other words, using the regression model to establish the relationship or indeed the correlation between each identified delay factor (the independent variable) and the dependent variable (delay in the port). This calls for the calculation of the Beta coefficients of the multi-regression.

As earlier explained, the regression analysis will be conducted using ship turnaround time or delay in port as the dependent variable (Y) and the identified causative factors or variables ($X_1 - X_{10}$) as independent variables. This is a forecasting technique which could be adopted to forecast delay factors in study location Apapa ports complex. The interpretation of the results of the regression analysis hovers around stepwise multi-regression coefficient denoted by R and is given by the formulae

$$R = \frac{\sum xy - \frac{\sum(x) \cdot \sum(y)}{n}}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2}{n}\right) \left(\frac{\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2}{n}\right)}}$$

The value of $R = -1$ indicates a perfect linear relationship between the sample value of X and Y , with the value of Y decreasing as the value of X increases. The larger X becomes, the smaller Y become and vice versa. A value of $R = +1$ also indicates a perfect relationship between y and x but here y increases as x increases. Larger values of y are associated with larger values of x .

If there is no relationship between the samples of y and x , to zero. As R increases from 0 to -1, the relationship between the sample value of x and y becomes more pronounced.

Table 7: The Cumulative Ranking Of Delay Factors At Apapa Ports Complex January – December 2007

Months	Delay in days	IADB X ₁	LCHE X ₂	LMP X ₃	SSMP X ₄	ADBN X ₅	DADPU X ₆	LSF X ₇	INDECH X ₈	TMPHS X ₉	TNIDTEF X ₁₀
JAN	10.02	182	162	174	186	296	274	200	150	160	112
FEB	10.37	160	154	124	176	294	300	156	176	130	96
MARCH	8.75	174	242	96	184	322	260	240	154	112	86
APRIL	11.24	124	195	102	154	284	254	210	167	102	104
MAY	10.40	96	122	94	183	244	190	125	135	144	150
JUNE	13.08	102	154	86	96	276	290	140	108	96	100
JULY	10.68	86	150	75	102	285	260	150	125	86	154
AUG	13.24	56	160	66	80	340	280	102	96	74	96
SEPT	14.06	160	200	104	160	274	180	196	150	142	102
OCT	12.36	175	140	130	187	296	200	184	140	120	96
NOV	14.45	188	168	100	145	286	202	210	150	102	100
DEC	15.63	202	187	155	198	244	184	200	168	123	104
TOTAL	144.28	1705	2034	1306	1851	3441	2874	2113	1719	1391	1300
AVERAGE	12.02	142.08	169.50	108.33	124.24	286.75	239.50	176.08	143.25	115.92	108.33
AVERAGE	12.02	44.87	53.53	34.37	48.71	90.55	75.63	55.61	45.24	36.61	34.21

SOURCE: field work computation

Table8: The Regression Statistics Of Apapa Ports Complex

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std Error of the estimate	R square change	Change statistics			Sig. F change	Durbin watson
						F change	df1	df2		
1	0.998 ^a	0.997	0.963	0.40099	0.997	29.920	10	1	0.141	2.405

a. Predictor: (constant) TMIDT, TMPHS, DADPU, LCHE, INDEC, ADBN, LMPW, LSF, SSMP, IADB

b. Dependent variable: delay

ANOVA

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
1. Regression	48.109	10	4.811	29.920	0.141 ^a
Residual	0.161	1	0.161		
Total	48.270	11			

(a) Predictor: (constant), TMIDT, TMPHS, DADPU, LCHE, INDEC, ADBN, LMPW, LSF, SSMP, IADB

(b) Dependent variable: delay

Table 9: Regression Results For Apapa Ports Complex Delay Causative Factors

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig.	95% confidence interval for B		correlations		
	B	Std Error	Beta			Lower bound	Upper bound	Zero-order	Partial	part
(constant)	-8.647	.968		-8.936	.071	-2.014	79.768			
IABX ₁	-1.334	.335	-.113	-3.976	.157	-.102	.135	.163	.869	.101
LCHEX ₂	30.337	.569	.826	34.918	0.018	-.090	.118	-.040	0.863	.099
LMPX ₃	-6.183	.696	-.195	-8.889	0.071	-.072	.154	.037	.978	.269
SSMPX ₄	9.930	.375	.742	26.469	.024	-0.170	.046	-.180	-.991	-.420
ADBNX ₅	19.937	.463	1.579	43.016	0.015	-.121	.073	-.313	-.951	-.178
DADPU X ₆	9.418	.446	.766	21.21	.030	-.101	.018	-.501	-.994	-.513
LSF X ₇	-9.921	.435	-.878	-22.783	0.028	-.150	.084	-.052	-.964	-.208
INDECH X ₈	7.528	.360	.602	20.898	.030	-.118	.166	-.108	-.906	.124
TMPHS X ₉	5.661	.600	.292	9.443	.067	-.141	.099	-.203	-.911	-.128
TMIDTEF X ₁₀	-19.889	.814	-.828	-24.40	.026	-.177	.086	-.236	-.975	-.255

Identification of the Critical Factors for Apapa Ports Complex from the Regression Analysis

The regression statistics as shown on table 8 shows a strong correlation existing between delay values and the identified causative factors. The R value stood at 0.988 or 98.8% the coefficient of determination also gave a high value of 99.7%. this implies that the causative factors X_1 - X_{10} is accountable for the delay experienced at the port to the tune of 99.7%.

Looking at table 8 also shows the Beta values of the delay causative factors relative to the turnaround time of shops at the port. The negative contributors to the delay values at Apapa ports complex are variables X_1 , X_3 , X_7 and X_{10} . Each of these factors has negative Beta coefficients.

Considering the factors that have positive Beta values for the selection of the critical factors, we present X_2 whose Beta value is 30.337. this is followed by variable X_5 with Beta value 19.937, X_4 with B 9.930, X_6 with B 9.418, $X_8 = 7.528$ and $X_9 = 5.661$. from these Beta values, the factor with the highest Beta coefficient becomes the most critical factor relative to Apapa ports complex delay problems. Consequently, variable X_2 whose Beta value stood at 30.337 is the most critical factor. The next influential factors to the delay values in descending order are $X_5 = 19.937$, $X_4 = 9.930$, $X_6 = 9.418$, $X_8 = 7.528$ and $X_9 = 5.661$

Discussions on the Critical Factors

The identification of variable X_2 or lack of enough functional cargo handling equipment at the port as the most critical factor is justified. Though the private operators have invested much resources in the procurement of cargo handling equipment in both quantity and quality, the investment result or effect is not yet significant. The terminal operators still rely mostly on the outdated and obsolete equipment inherited from Nigerian ports authority during the concession arrangement. This factor is the bane of efficient port operation in Nigeria.

The next most critical factors are administrative bottleneck X_5 and extortion of money X_6 . The duo combining termed corruption at the port is important for to be addressed for to be addressed if port efficiency could be improved. The next critical variable X_8 or shallowness of the entry channel is an important efficiency mitigating factor at Apapa ports complex. The advent of larger capacity vessels calls for constant dredging of the entry channels to the port. The dredging of the entry channel has its problem to surmount. The constant dredging to float in the giant vessels now trading between Europe, America, Far East and African ports calls for additional operating cost. When the additional cost is imputed into the port charges for calling ships, port cost escalates to the detriment of the developing countries' economies.

The non inclusion of inadequacies of berthing facilities as a positive contributory factor to delays in Apapa ports complex is justified the advent of Jumbo vessels and the consequent calls Apapa port means reduction in the volume vessels traffic to the port. This is the main problem of the study. The situation whereby most of the berths remain empty often yet the port continued to go high justify the study.

The non-inclusion of lack of manpower X_3 as a positive contribution factor to delay level observed at the Apapa port is also justified. A country with a high rate of employment cannot lack manpower at the port industry. The new private operators inherited large volume of unskilled dockworkers, therefore retraining of dockworkers is a problem, consequently scarcity of skilled manpower, X_4 is a positive contributory variable to delays at the port. The result of the regression analysis shows that lack of storage facilities or variable X_7 is not a positive contributor to delay at the port. The presence of numerous private bounded warehouses in Lagos means that the factor X_7 is not a critical factor relative to the problem of efficiency in Apapa ports complex. The variable X_9 or too much public holidays is a positive contributory factor. Though the staff of the private port operators do not observe public holidays but the activities of the other service providers at the port (the customs, NDLEA, the pilots, NAFDAC etc) do observe public holidays. Also the implementation of night operations by these government agencies is another problem militating against improved turnaround time at the port.

THE CONSTRUCTION OF A REGRESSION MODEL FOR APAPA PORTS COMPLEX

From the Beta values displayed on table 9, the multi regression equation for Apapa ports complex is as follows

$$AVTRAD/DELAY = -8.647 - 1.334X_1 + 30.337X_2 - 6.183X_3 + 9.930X_4 + 19.937X_5 + 9.418X_6 - 9.921X_7 + 70528X_8 + 50661X_9 - 19.889X_{10} + e$$

The equation suggests that delay will increase on average by 1.334 of a unit decrease in X_1 , increase on average by 30.337 of a unit increase in X_2 , increase on an average of 6.183 of a unit decrease in X_3 increase on average by 9.930 of a unit increase in X_4 , increase on average by 19.937 of a unit increase in X_5 , increase on

average by 9.921 of a unit decrease in X_7 , increase on average by 7.528 of a unit increase in X_8 , increase on average by 5.661 of a unit increase in X_9 , increase on average by 19.889 of a unit decrease in X_{10} .

Consequently the study suggests that to improve on the turnaround time of ships calling at Apapa ports complex, attention must be given to the problems of lack of cargo handling equipment, the presence of an administrative bottleneck, extortion of money deliberately from port users, scarcity of skilled manpower, problem of non-implementation of night operation in the port and too much public holidays by other service providers outside the staff of the private terminal operators

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